

A Retrospective Look at the Conservation and Restoration of Large Technology Objects Carried Out at the Australian War Memorial during the 1960's to the 1980's.

George Bailey, A/g Manager, Preventive, Objects and Large Technology Conservation, Australian War Memorial.

ABSTRACT

From the 1970's until the mid-1980's the Australian War Memorial was largely underfunded and under resourced. During this period some work was carried out on the larger objects within the collection, with mixed results. Some large objects were treated in-house by staff, some by Australia's defence forces, others by private defence contractors, and yet others were treated for free by private companies or individuals. Many objects were left untouched in storage and time has proved that this often turned out to be a good thing. In each category mentioned above, there were both good outcomes and, with the benefit of hindsight, some professionally and financially painful outcomes. Case histories of an Avro Lancaster, de Havilland Mosquito, Mitsubishi Zero, Japanese Type 94 Tankette, Renault FT-17 Light Tank, Pfalz D.XII Scout Aircraft, Albatros D.Va scout aircraft, Messerschmitt Me 262 A-2, German 8.8 cm Flak 18/36 Dual Purpose antiaircraft/antitank gun, Japanese Midget Submarine, German Fritz X Guided Missile, and a German Henschel Hs 293 Glide Bomb are all examined, discussed in detail and conclusions drawn.

INTRODUCTION

The Australian War Memorial (AWM) was a somewhat stagnant place in the 1960's and 70's¹ due in part to a lack of funding, and in part to a lack of willingness by senior management to evolve and grow. It wasn't until recommendations in the Pigott Report² were progressively implemented in the late 1970's to early 1980 that the AWM started to grow and start the transition from a backwater in the museum world to the world class cultural heritage institution that it is today.

The lack of funding was not unique to the AWM. In the 1960's and 70's there was a general run down and malaise in the museum sector in Australia, which prompted the Federal Government to establish the Committee of Inquiry on Museums and National Collections in 1974. The fact that during that period Australia was involved in the Vietnam War, which was very unpopular with the general public, didn't help the AWM's cause.

Nonetheless, despite lack of funding and stagnation, the AWM's collection of large technology did receive some attention, with varying degrees of success, as will be seen in the following case studies.

Avro Lancaster

The Avro Lancaster Mk I “G for George” is probably the best known object within the AWM’s collection. Taken out of service from 460 Squadron, RAAF, in England, 1944, the aircraft was refurbished and repainted before flying out to Australia where it was flown around the country on War Bonds tours in 1944-45. The aircraft was then parked at RAAF Fairbairn base in Canberra, where it stayed for the next 10 years, much of it outdoors. During this time, the aircraft suffered the effects of the elements and vandalism and theft of parts. In 1955, the AWM was finally in a position to accept and display the Lancaster in its’ Aircraft Hall. Concerns were held about the floor loading in Aircraft Hall, so a directive was given to the RAAF, who dismantled, installed and reassembled the aircraft in the hall, to lighten the aircraft. In addition to the many internal fittings already stolen, much of what was left of the interior was literally smashed off. The aircraft was also given a coat of matt black and what can best be described as a rather horrible overall brown colour, instead of green and brown camouflage. In 1978 the aircraft was again repainted, this time at least in green/brown camouflage, even if the markings and camouflage pattern were incorrect³. The rumour within the AWM is that the paint scheme was based on an Airfix scale model kit.

Throughout the 1980’s some effort was put in to restoring the interior of the aircraft. Some missing parts and fittings were acquired, and repairs were carried to some of the damage caused between 1945 -55. The repair work carried out was of varying quality, and poorly recorded.

In 1999 the Lancaster was disassembled and taken to the AWM’s Conservation annex for restoration and conservation, for display in the new AWM’s new ANZAC Hall. A lot of time and effort was put in to identifying original markings, damage and repairs from when the aircraft served with 460 squadron between 1942 and 1944. The markings from that period were replicated, including mistakes, and the repairs were retained. Repairs carried out at the Memorial between 1955 and 1999 were assessed for quality and “correct method” and replaced where needed. The aircraft was repainted in colours and patterns that the aircraft wore in 1944.

Figure 1. Avro Lancaster Mk I “G-George” on display in ANZAC Hall, Australian War Memorial 2013.

de Havilland Mosquito

The AWM’s de Havilland Mosquito was acquired in the early 1980’s as a type example. It was in a very poor state, with much of the timber rotted and structurally unstable. An agreement was reached with Hawker de Havilland, a descendant of the company that originally made the aircraft, to restore it using apprentice labour with the AWM paying for materials used. Curatorial and conservation input was used to guide the restoration process, but over more than a decade the project gradually lost momentum as Hawker de Havilland scaled back its apprenticeship programme until finally, in 1996, the company informed the AWM that it could no longer continue with the programme. By this time, the AWM had established a large conservation/restoration facility and had the resources to retrieve the aircraft and complete the restoration in-house.

Figure 2 de Havilland Mosquito in Aircraft Hall, Australian War Memorial, 2013.

Mitsubishi A6M2 Zero

The AWM's Mitsubishi A6M2 Zero was damaged in action and abandoned on the island of Gasmata in 1943. It was later captured and transported back to Australia for evaluation and analysis. By the time it arrived at the AWM it was pretty much a wreck. The director at the time – Air Vice Marshal (retired) Jim Flemming – used his contacts within the RAAF to arrange for the aircraft to be restored by apprentice aircraftsmen. There was little conservation input into this project, but at least curatorial guidelines were developed, and a project manager appointed to coordinate the purchase and supply of materials and parts needed.

The resulting restored aircraft is an example of high quality work carried out by the RAAF apprentices, but much original material and markings were lost in the process, and few parts that were replaced were returned to the AWM.

Figure 3. Mitsubishi A6M2 Zero on display in Aircraft Hall, Australian War Memorial 2013.

German 8.8 cm Flak 18/36 Dual Purpose Gun.

The AWM's Flak 36 was one of at least two Flak 36 Anti Aircraft Guns which arrived in Sydney, New South Wales, in March 1943. The gun was used by the German Afrika Korps in North Africa and was captured by Australian troops sometime between 23 October and 4 November 1942, possibly at El Alamein together with one anti-tank gun. Signatures and service numbers scratched into the gun indicate that 2/2 Australian Line of Communication Recovery Section and 2/1 Australian Army Field Workshop Recovery Unit were involved in the salvaging of this weapon. The AWM held the gun until April 1958 when it was donated to 1 Field Regiment, Royal Australian Artillery. It was reacquired by the AWM in December 1977 and was used as an outside display until 1988.

In 1988 the gun was transported to Australian Defence Industries (ADI), in Victoria, where restoration work was carried out. ADI carried out the work at no cost to the AWM. By 1988, the AWM had a functioning Conservation section and more curatorial resources. In-house investigations into the original paint colours were carried out, and curatorial guidelines regarding markings, etc, were available to guide the restoration. Original battle damage was

retained. In hindsight, more of the original paint could probably have been saved, but at least the resulting restoration is in keeping with the original finish of the gun.

Figure 4. German 8.8 cm Flak 18/36 Dual Purpose Gun on display in ANZAC Hall, Australian War Memorial 2013.

Japanese Type A Midget Submarine.

The AWM's Type A midget submarine is a composite of two of the three midget submarines that raided Sydney Harbour on 1 June 1942 while attempting to destroy Australian and American warships. One submarine was destroyed by depth charges; the other became entangled in the anti-submarine nets at the harbour entrance and was scuttled by its crew. The third submarine escaped, and was only recently discovered off the NSW coast. Some days after 1 June, 1942, the submarines were recovered from the harbour and pieces were sent on a War Bonds tour around eastern Australia.

After the war, the nose section of one submarine, and the centre and tail sections of the other were transferred to the AWM, where they were displayed outside until the 1980's, receiving numerous coats of black paint over the years. By the 1980's the submarine was suffering extensive corrosion from prolonged outdoor exposure, so it was sent to the Cockatoo Island

Dockyard for restoration by naval apprentices. As with the Flak 36 mentioned earlier, considerable conservation and curatorial effort was invested in analysing paintwork and materials used on the submarine, and these guided the restoration.

In the late 1990's further conservation work was carried out, this time by in-house staff. Investigations into the exterior surface identified a number of witness marks punched into the skin. These matched with markings on other midget submarines photos found in internet searches, and so were painted on.

Figure 5. Japanese Type A Midget Submarine on display in ANZAC Hall, Australian War Memorial 2013.

French Renault FT17 Light Tank

The French Renault FT 17 light tank was acquired by the AWM just after the First World War. When acquired, it was originally dark grey in colour. In the 1960's staff repainted the tank in the current three tone camouflage system, possibly someone had seen similar tanks in European museums that were in three tone camouflage schemes, or possibly in an attempt to brighten the galleries up, although no record was kept of who made the decision or who carried out the work. The latter is probably the reason, because a number of large objects on

display in the AWM galleries during that period were also painted, with scant regard for original colour schemes. Fortunately, the preparation work carried out was minimal, and much of the original paintwork still survives under the existing paint scheme.

Figure 6. French Renault FT 17 Light Tank at the Australian War Memorial's Treloar Conservation Annex, 2013.

Japanese Type 94, Model 2594 Tankette

The AWM's Type 94, Model 2594 Tankette was captured by the 2/9th Battalion, AIF in the town of Klandasan, Balikpapan, Borneo on the 1 July 1945. The tankette was shipped to Australia aboard SS *Winchester Victory* in December 1945 and was transferred to the AWM soon after.

As with the Renault tank mentioned above, this tank was repainted during the 1960's whilst it was on display. The colour scheme used was at least a little more sympathetic than was applied to the Renault. A gloss colour scheme of bright yellow, bright green and rust-red was applied over the original matt sand yellow/olive green/rust red/earth brown camouflage scheme, with no attempt made to follow the original demarcation lines. Fortunately, the rear hatch had been taken off and put into store and was thus never repainted. The hatch has all original four colours on it. Again as with the Renault, surface preparation was minimal, and much of the original paint remains, as well as signatures scratched into the original paint by soldiers in 1945.

Figure 7. Japanese Tankette Type 94, Model 2594 at the Australian War Memorial's Treloar Conservation Annex, 2013.

German Pfalz D.XII and Albatros D.Va Scouts

The Pfalz D.XII biplane scout/fighter aircraft, serial no. 2600/18 and Albatros D.Va biplane scout/fighter aircraft, serial no. D5390/17 arrived at the AWM in the early 1920's. The Pfalz given to Australia under the terms of the Armistice, and the Albatros was a war trophy, being captured by 3 Squadron, Australian Flying Corps in December 1917.

Both aircraft were displayed in the AWM's Aircraft Hall from 1942 until the late 1960's. Neither aircraft had received much attention since being captured, and by the late 1960's were definitely showing their age. At around this time, a small aviation maintenance company that specialised in fabric covered aircraft offered to restore both biplanes for free. This offer was duly accepted, and the aircraft were dismantled and shipped some 200 km to the company's premises.

There appears to have been very little involvement by the AWM in the work carried out. The engines were swapped between the aircraft, and many minor repairs were crudely carried out. The spinner backing plate on the Albatros was installed back to front, and rather than

removing it and putting it back on correctly, it was beaten into submission to allow the spinner to fit.

The original cellulose nitrate doped linen fabrics were replaced with cellulose butyrate doped synthetic material that, although it was lozenge patterned, was not of the same colours. Very little of the original fabric was returned to the AWM. Rumours that pieces of genuine First World War German aircraft fabric later appeared for sale in one of Australia's aviation magazines in the early 1970's have not been substantiated at the time of writing.

Over nearly 40 years since the restorations were completed, the butyrate dope continued to shrink, resulting in the fabric tearing under its' own stresses, and some damage to the fragile structures within the wings. In the 1980's the AWM's aircraft curator, John White, worked on a joint project with the National Air and Space Museum (NASM) to use the remaining fabric samples from the AWM aircraft and similar aircraft at NASM to establish the colours and patterns of the original lozenge patterned camouflage system, and bolts of linen were dyed in sufficient quantities to satisfy both institutions needs for future restoration work. The AWM's aircraft were re-restored in-house in the early 2000's.

Figure 8. Pfalz D.XII on display in ANZAC Hall, AWM 2013.

Figure 9. Albatros D.Va on display in ANZAC Hall, AWM 2013.

Messerschmitt Me 262A-2

The AWM's Messerschmitt Me 262A-2 served with the German bomber unit KG51 in Germany and Czechoslovakia with the identity 'Black X'. In May 1945 it was flown to Fassberg and surrendered to the British by its pilot, Lieutenant Froelich. In late August it was later flown via Lubeck and RAF Manston, to the Royal Aircraft Establishment in Farnborough, United Kingdom, arriving on 6 September 1945. It was subsequently flown nine times by Royal Australian Engineer test pilots and later shipped to Australia. The

aircraft was displayed at the Australian War Memorial from 1955 until c 1970 and then loaned to RAAF museum, Point Cook, Victoria (Vic). At some stage, the aircraft was repainted, with incorrect camouflage scheme and colours, and incorrect type and placement of the Luftwaffe markings.

Figure 10. Messerschmitt Me 262A-2 on display in ANZAC Hall, Australian War Memorial 2013.

In 1981 the aircraft was transferred to the Commonwealth Aircraft Corporation (CAC) for restoration. Sections of the overlying paint were sanded back to reveal the aircraft's original markings and identity including the serial number 500200 (previously thought to be 500210), the red nose and tail tip; British Air Ministry marking AIR MIN 81 on the fuselage; the original Luftwaffe crosses; and the British roundels. For a number of reasons, the restoration project never really gained momentum, and aside from the sanding back the over-paint, the only work carried out was the replacement of several underwing panels. In retrospect, this was fortuitous, because much of the original material of the aircraft, including its roughly made appearance would probably have been lost forever.

Figure 11. Messerschmitt Me 262A-2 on display in ANZAC Hall, Australian War Memorial 2013.

Fritz X and Henschel 293 Guided Bombs.

The AWM's Fritz X and Henschel 293 guided bombs were acquired in the mid 1940's as war trophies. For most of their time at the AWM, they have been stored out of sight and out of mind. Aside from the occasional dusting and a dedicated transport stand made for the Henschel to make moving it easier, no conservation work has been carried out. They are, in effect, time capsules. The Fritz X is believed to be the only unrestored example of its type left in the world.

The paint on the warheads on both bombs show signs of burning, and it was not until the restoration of the AWM's V1 flying bomb, the warhead of which was also burnt, that a reasonable explanation was hypothesised. The explosive components were burnt out to render the bombs safe and the heat from this process charred the paintwork.

Figure 12 Fritz X guided bomb.

Figure 13. Henschel 293 guided bomb.

CONCLUSION

Many lessons can be learned from looking back at what was done in the past. Offers such as free restorations that sound too good to be true often turn out to be just that. The motives of such offers need to be carefully examined. Strong, detailed curatorial and conservation guidelines need to be prepared for any restoration, and regular inspections of the work should be carried out to ensure the quality of the work is of appropriate standard. All material that is replaced during a restoration should be returned to the museum, no matter how degraded or insignificant the parts may seem. Sometimes, doing nothing at all turns out to be the right thing to do in the long run.

REFERENCES

1. M^cKernan, M. **Here is their spirit: a history of the Australian War Memorial 1917-1990.** St. Lucia, Qld.: University of Queensland Press in association with the Australian War Memorial, 1991.
2. P H Pigott, **National Museums in Australia 1975: Report of the Committee of Inquiry on Museums and National Collections including the Report of the Planning Committee on the Gallery of Aboriginal Australia.**, Australian Government Publishing Service, Canberra, 1975.
3. Nelmes, M. & Jenkins, I. **G-For George: A memorial to RAAF Bomber Crews 1939-45.** Banner Books, Maryborough, Qld, 2000.